

ACRP

Final Report – Activity Report

Program control:

Climate and Energy Fund

Program management:

Kommunalkredit Public Consulting GmbH (KPC)

1 Project Data

Short title	PURIFY	
Full title	Effects of desiccation on the self-purification capacity of headwater streams: Consequences for the stream management	
Project number	B769828 KR17AC0K13643	
Program/Program line	ACRP 10 th Call for Proposals	
Applicant	WasserCluster Lunz – Biologische Station GmbH Dr. Gabriele Weigelhofer	
Project partners	Universität für Bodenkultur, IWA, Priv.-Doz. DI Dr. Michael Tritthart, Vienna University of Barcelona, Dr. Daniel von Schiller, Spain ¹ TU Brandenburg, Apl. Prof. Dr Michael Mutz, Germany	
Project start and duration	Project start: 01.04.2018	Duration: 42 months
Reporting period	from 01.04.2018 to 30.09.2021	

¹ Due to the new position of Daniel von Schiller at the University of Barcelona, we requested a change of partner 2 from the University of the Basque Country to the University of Barcelona. The change was accepted by Klimafond, all partner contracts were adapted, and the budget was transferred accordingly.

Synopsis:

The project aimed at analysing the effects of drying and rewetting on the self-purification capacity and the water quality of intermittent streams in Burgenland, Carinthia, Styria, and Lower Austria. We sampled streams before and during the dry period, analysed water and sediment quality, nutrient retention, and the activity of biofilms, and performed laboratory experiments. Intermittent streams hold a high remaining water content in the sediments during drought which helped to keep the biofilms intact. In general, nutrient uptake, microbial respiration, and photosynthesis were lower in dry than in wet sediments and algae were more impacted by drying than bacteria. However, recovery of both the microbial community and the sediment processes after flow resumption was fast and no long-term effects were observed.

Project abstract

Over the past thirty years, the frequency and duration of droughts has increased dramatically across Europe, exposing Austrian streams to increasing pressure from periodic desiccation during which surface water flow is disrupted (intermittency). Desiccation may harm the microbial biofilm community and alter the resource supply in the sediments, thus impairing the self-purification capacity and reducing the water quality of the affected streams. Despite a current boom in intermittent rivers' research in Mediterranean and arid regions, knowledge about the effects of intermittency on stream functions is still marginal especially in temperate regions and strategies for the assessment and sustainable management of intermittent streams are lacking. The project PURIFY aimed to advance intermittent stream research in Austria and support environmental authorities in the protection and management of intermittent streams by setting the following objectives:

- Analysing the medium- to long-term effects of intermittent flow on stream ecosystems' structures and functions determining the water quality of intermittent streams in Austria
- Quantifying potential effects of desiccation on the self-purification capacity of stream sediments and identifying factors responsible for the resistance and resilience to desiccation
- Modelling potential consequences of drought for the water quality and related ecosystem functions in selected streams in Austria
- Developing a guideline for water management authorities to assess the risks of a possible deterioration of water quality due to droughts

The data collection was divided between three work packages (WP). In WP2, we investigated the medium- to short-term effects of intermittent flow on the water quality and the biogeochemical processes in intermittent stream reaches via field sampling. We selected 10-12 low to moderately polluted intermittent and perennial stream reaches, respectively, in Carinthia, Burgenland, Styria, and Lower Austria. Water and sediments from the benthic and the hyporheic zone were sampled before and during the dry phase in 2018 and 2019 and were analysed for nutrient and organic matter concentrations, microbial biomass, and the activity of the biofilms (e.g. respiration, mineralisation, nutrient uptake). Dry sediments from intermittent reaches showed similar bacterial abundances, chlorophyll-a concentrations, and enzymatic activities as wet sediments from perennial reaches, while respiration rates, ammonium uptake rates, and photosynthetic efficiencies were lower in dry sediments. Thus, biofilm processes were more affected than biofilm structures. We attribute the high resistance of structures to the fact that the temperate climate and shading helped to maintain a relatively high water content even after several months of desiccation. Thus, biofilm communities were able to survive within this thin water film. In contrast, unsaturated conditions in the sediments changed the supply with oxygen, nutrients, and organic matter, thus affecting biogeochemical processes. Interestingly, we observed high nutrient concentrations in the remaining stream water of perennial reaches during drought, probably

due to nutrient release from sediments under increased water temperature and lack of dilution.

In WP3, we looked more closely into the effects of drying and rewetting on the nutrient and organic matter uptake capacity of the sediment surface and the hyporheic zone of 10 intermittent and 10 perennial study reaches via laboratory experiments with flumes and sediment perfusion cores. For this purpose, large stones from the sediment surface and fine sediments from 20-30 cm sediment depth were sampled before the non-flow period in spring 2019. The stones were incubated in laboratory flumes, the fine sediments were filled in vertical sediment columns, both flown through with nutrient-poor water. After an adaptation phase, both systems were dried out and rewetted under controlled conditions. Before, during, and after the dry period, we performed nutrient and organic matter uptake experiments and measured microbial activities and abundances. The algal biofilms of both intermittent and perennial reaches showed significantly reduced photosynthetic activities and nutrient uptake capacities which did not recover within the two weeks recovery phase. The hyporheic sediments showed a short, but significant release of nutrients and organic carbon immediately upon rewetting. Nutrient uptake was reduced for some days after rewetting, but usually recovered within one week. Intermittent and perennial reaches did also not differ significantly in their response to drying. Thus, the experiments confirmed the field data by demonstrating high resistance and resilience of stream sediments to drying and rewetting.

In WP4, two-dimensional hydrodynamic models (RSim-2D) of three representative study reaches were developed to analyse changes in biogeochemical functions at different discharges. The models were based on the geodetic and discharge data of Glauningbach (Styria), Reitschulbach (Burgenland) and Sucha (Carinthia). Simulations were carried out for three to four different discharges and the hydrodynamic models were blended with CO₂ production data of WP2. The CO₂ production at different wetted areas in the river bed allowed conclusions on the effect of changing flow regimes on biogeochemical processes in the river.

The project shows that stream biofilms responsible for water purification are hardly harmed by even prolonged intermittent flow conditions in Austrian streams due to the relatively high remaining moisture content in the sediments. However, low flow conditions during summer may impair the water quality due to nutrient release from the sediments. Further research should focus on the interactive effects of low flow and increased water temperatures on the nutrient release potential of the sediments and its significance for the water quality under different environmental conditions.

Contents and results of the project

1. *Initial situation / motivation for the project*

Climate change has been a threat for the integrity of freshwater ecosystems for decades (Vörösmarty et al. 2000), causing water scarcity and droughts to become a major environmental challenge in the 21st century (Lake 2003; Ledger et al. 2012). Droughts have spread across Europe (IPCC 2014), shifting perennial streams to intermittent flow regimes even in temperate zones (Datry et al. 2014; Sabater et al. 2016). Water abstraction for irrigation, extended drainage of arable land, and the loss of natural water retention areas have aggravated the situation further (Kaletová et al. 2019).

One of the most important ecosystem services of headwater streams is their capacity to transform and retain dissolved and particulate nutrients and organic matter imported from the terrestrial catchment, a function which provides the base for good water quality in receiving downstream water bodies (Peterson et al. 2001). As the drying of river beds may harm aquatic microbes and significantly alter biogeochemical and microbial transformation processes in the sediments (Marxsen et al. 2010; Febria et al. 2012; Timoner et al. 2012, 2014; Sabater et al. 2016; Von Schiller et al. 2017), this natural self-purification capacity may be impacted. Despite the large number of studies in intermittent Mediterranean and semi-arid/arid streams during the last decade (e.g. Datry et al. 2011; von Schiller et al. 2011; Bernal et al. 2013; Romani et al. 2013), little is known so far about the impacts of drought on the biogeochemical and microbial processes in the sediments of streams in temperate regions and the consequences for the water quality (but see Marxsen et al. 2010; Ledger et al. 2012). However, in the face of increasing drought probability in the future, it is imperative for stream managers to know about the effects of intermittent flow on stream ecosystem structures and processes and to be able to assess drought consequences for the self-purification capacity and the water quality of affected streams. Furthermore, managers need to dispose of risk assessment methods which enable them to identify streams specifically vulnerable to drought impacts on the water quality.

2. *Objectives of the project*

The study aimed to advance intermittent stream research and support Austrian environmental authorities in the protection and sustainable management of intermittent streams by setting the following objectives:

- Investigate the medium- and long-term effects of drought on ecosystem structures and functions determining the water quality of intermittent streams in Austria
- Analyse the potential effects of desiccation on the self-purification capacity of the sediment surface and the hyporheic zone
- Identify factors which determine the resilience and vulnerability of streams to drought impacts

- Model potential consequences of drought for the water quality of intermittent streams in Austria
- Develop a guideline for water management authorities containing a risk assessment method for a possible deterioration of water quality due to drought

3. *Activities performed within the framework of the project, including methods employed*
In **WP1** (Project management and dissemination), we coordinated the project, developed a project website (www.intermittentstreams.at), and presented the project on the websites of all partners as well as in the media.

In WP2, we investigated the long- to short-term effects of riverbed drying on the biogeochemical and microbial processes on the sediment surface and in the hyporheic zone of 10-12 intermittent stream reaches along a land use gradient in southern Carinthia, Burgenland, Styria, and Lower Austria. We sampled sediments before (long-term) and during (short-term) the non-flow phase in the intermittent reaches and additionally in 10-12 perennial reaches with comparable hydro-morphology and water quality for comparisons and also to identify potential seasonal effects. The samplings were performed in 2018 (dry summer), 2019 (wet summer) and partly in 2020 (intermediate summer). The sediment samples were analysed for moisture content, nutrient and organic matter contents, bacterial abundances, chlorophyll-a, pigment compositions, and the activity of the biofilms (e.g. respiration, mineralisation, nutrient uptake, and primary production). Additionally, we took water samples in the perennial reaches and during flowing conditions in the intermittent reaches.

In WP3, we analysed the effects of drying and re-wetting on the nutrient and organic matter uptake capacity of the sediment surface and the hyporheic zone of 10 intermittent and 10 perennial study reaches via experimental flumes and sediment perfusion cores in the laboratory. Hyporheic sediments were sampled from 20-30 cm depth in spring 2019, filled into the sediment cores in the field (pre-sieved to 2 – 6.3 mm to avoid clogging) and brought to the lab. After a climatization phase of two weeks, during which water was pumped from bottom to top through the cores in flow-through mode, the cores were drained and dried out for seven weeks, then re-wetted under controlled conditions and kept for another two weeks in flow-through mode. Before, during, and several times (1d, 2d, 1 week, 2 weeks) after the dry period, dissolved nutrient and organic matter addition experiments were performed with soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP), ammonium (NH₄-N), DOC in the form of leaf leachate and ¹⁵N-NO₃, and uptake or release rates were calculated under ambient and enriched conditions. In addition, chemical and microbial parameters were analysed in the sediments before and after the experiment. We used synergies with another project dealing with dissolved organic matter degradation to analyse hyporheic respiration in the 20 study streams under ambient, soil leachate enriched, and soil leachate plus phosphate enriched conditions.

In a second experiment, we sampled 6-8 stones from the surface of each study reach and incubated them in laboratory flumes (one per reach; flumes consisted of transparent Plexiglas and were 0.5 m long and 7 cm wide) under flowing conditions (10h daylight/ 14 h dark). After two weeks of acclimatisation, the flumes were drained and kept dry for three weeks. Then, water flow was resumed. We measured nutrient uptake, oxygen consumption and production before drying and after rewetting, and the composition of the biofilms.

In **WP4**, two-dimensional hydrodynamic models (RSim-2D) of three representative study reaches were developed to analyse changes in biogeochemical functions at different discharges and water levels, respectively. In 2018, geodetic data of Glauningbach (Styria), Reitschulbach (Burgenland) and Sucha (Carinthia) were generated and simulations of steady state flow in the selected reaches were carried out. Based on discharges observed using pressure gauges (installed during the first project year), simulations were carried out for three to four different discharges. The wetted area at each flow rate was exported as a GIS compatible shape file and its areal extent was measured. In addition, the wetted flow area remaining after reductions of the flow rate to approximately 10% or less of the measured flow rate was exported. This state is representative of a situation with minimum flow where only wetted pools remain. The comparison of different discharge scenarios yielded potential drought consequences for different biofilm functions.

In **WP5**, we developed a guideline for managers containing a risk assessment of potential water quality deterioration due to drought and suggestions for stream monitoring.

4. *Description of the results and project milestones*

Work package 1: Project management and dissemination

- ✓ MS1: Project description for partner homepages
- ✓ MS2: Project homepage
- ✓ MS3, MS4, MS6: Annual reports
- ✓ MS5: Manuscript for synthesis paper: *Feldbacher E, D von Schiller, M Mutz, L Coulson, M Tritthart, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Freshwater Biology) Impacts of intermittent flow on benthic biofilm processes and structures in temperate-climate streams*

Work package 2: Field data

In 2018, only six perennial and five intermittent headwater reaches in Burgenland and Styria were investigated which showed a similar hydro-morphology and water quality. The data showed surprisingly high average gravimetric moisture contents of about 10% and more in the unsaturated sediments of the intermittent reaches even after >2 months of disrupted surface flow (**Feldbacher et al., submitted**). Intermittent reaches did not differ from perennial reaches in spring and were also hardly affected by the non-flow phase in summer. Structural parameters in benthic biofilms (on both fine sediments and stone surfaces) only showed significant differences between perennial and intermittent reaches in the relative

proportion of carotenoids in algae. Here, fucoxanthin had significantly higher average proportions in perennial than in intermittent reaches both in spring and summer. In contrast, lutein proportions were significantly lower in perennial than in intermittent reaches. The relative proportion of all carotenoids was generally higher in perennial than in intermittent reaches contrary to reports from other studies. We suggest that the low effects of intermittent flow on algal biofilms were due to heavy shading of the study reaches which generally reduced algal growth in all streams. Also in contrast to other studies from drier regions, the activity of extra-cellular enzymes did not differ between intermittent and perennial reaches during the non-flow period nor did the enzymatic ratios differ (**Fig.1**).

Figure 1: Extra-cellular enzymatic activities (left graphs a, c) and ratios of enzymatic activities (right graphs b, d) in epipsammic biofilms (upper part a, b; n=24 – 41) and in epilithic biofilms (lower part c, d; n = 39 - 55) of perennial and intermittent reaches in spring and summer. Figures a, c show 10, 25, 50, 75, and 90 percentiles. From: Feldbacher et al. submitted

Among the analysed biogeochemical processes, benthic biofilms showed significant reductions of the respiratory capacity (by approx. -50% in fine sediments) and the photosynthetic efficiency (algal biofilms on stones), respectively. However, the photosynthetic efficiency was also reduced in perennial reaches in summer, indicating that

shading effects may have overlaid desiccation stress on epilithic biofilms. Unsaturated sediments of intermittent reaches showed an increased ammonium release and a significantly reduced ammonium uptake upon rewetting compared to the wet sediments of perennial reaches. However, this pattern was not observed for dissolved inorganic phosphorus (**Fig. 2**). We assume this pattern to reflect the general P-limitation of our streams.

Figure 2: SRP and NH₄-N release rates under ambient conditions (a) and exchange rates under nutrient enriched conditions (b) for epipsammic biofilms in summer; positive data present nutrient uptake, negative release; shown are 10, 25, 50, 75, and 90 percentiles and outliers (n = 15-25). From: Feldbacher et al. submitted

In 2019, a set of 10 intermittent and 10 perennial reaches across the four Austrian regions was investigated. Only fine sediments from the sediment surface were sampled in spring before the non-flow phase and in autumn during the non-flow phase. Additionally, sediments sampled in spring from both stream types were air-dried under a roof to protect them from rainfall.

The results show that – like in 2018 – sediments of intermittent streams were hardly affected by the non-flow period despite showing a significantly lower moisture content than the perennial streams (5-10%; **Fig. 3; Coulson et al, in prep**). Only respiration was significantly lower in the dry sediments. In comparison, air-drying led to decreased moisture contents in both intermittent and perennial stream sediments, whereby the moisture content was only slightly lower there than in the field samples (3-8%). Like the field samples, benthic respiration was reduced. We did not observe any significant differences between perennial and intermittent reaches in the dried sediments.

We also analysed water samples in 2018 and 2019 in perennial streams and in pools in intermittent streams. We observed high nutrient concentrations in the remaining stream water of perennial reaches during prolonged drought, probably due to nutrient release from sediments under increased water temperature and lack of dilution (Weigelhofer & Tritthart, 2019).

Figure 3: SRP and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ release rates under ambient conditions (a) and exchange rates under nutrient enriched conditions (b) for epipsammic biofilms in summer; positive data present nutrient uptake, negative release; shown are 10, 25, 50, 75, and 90 percentiles and outliers ($n = 15\text{-}25$). From: Coulson et al. in prep

Milestones of WP2:

- ✓ MS7: Manuscript for article in ÖWAW: Weigelhofer G. & M. Tritthart (2019) *Austrocknung von Bächen – eine Gefahr für die Wasserqualität? Österr Wasser- und Abfallw 2019 · 71:385–391. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00506-019-0580-2>*
- ✓ MS8: Sediment and water quality data from intermittent streams before, during and after drought; data will be made accessible in a repository after publication
- MS9: Manuscript about changes in biofilm structures and functions during intermittency in temperate streams: Coulson L, Feldbacher E, Weigelhofer G (in prep; draft existing) *Similar response of biofilms to drying in perennial and intermittent reaches of temperate-climate streams*

Work package 3: Laboratory experiments

Like the drying experiment in WP2, we did not observe any significant differences between intermittent and perennial stream sediments in their response to drying and rewetting in our column study (**Pucher et al submitted**). All sediments showed a short, but high release of nutrients and DOC immediately upon rewetting which lasted less than a day (**Fig. 4**). DOC and nutrient uptake rates were reduced after rewetting but usually recovered within two weeks. Thus, our laboratory experiment with controlled drying and rewetting confirmed our field results.

Figure 4: Release/retention rate of DOC, and nutrients past percolation through sediment cores during ambient conditions (left, violet) and nutrient additions (right, teal) before and after the drying phase (grey bar). The boxplots show the variability across all 20 cores of the measured data at their respective sampling day. The coloured ribbons show the 90% probability interval of the posterior distributions. The models with stream-specific random effects on r_0 were used to show the black recovery curve. From Pucher et al (submitted)

The algal biofilms on the stone surfaces showed significant reductions of the photosynthetic activities (**Fig. 5**) and the nutrient uptake capacities after the dry phase in both perennial and intermittent samples. Algae from open stream sections were stronger affected than those in shaded sections. We did not observe any recovery within the two weeks of the recovery phase. A manuscript about these results is currently in preparation (von Schiller et al. in prep).

Figure 5: Net primary production of epilithic biofilms before (initial) and 1d, 1wk, and 2wks after the dry phase. Orange = shaded streams in agricultural catchments, blue = open streams in forested catchments. From Von Schiller et al (in prep)

Finally, synergies with another project dealing with hyporheic respiration in our 20 study streams under ambient, soil leachate enriched, and phosphate enriched conditions has led to an additional manuscript (Attermeyer et al, submitted to Freshwater Biology).

Milestones:

- ✓ MS 10: Delivery of potential uptake rates for nutrients and DOC
- ✓ MS11: Manuscript about the potential SRP, nitrate and DOC uptake in hyporheic sediments exposed to desiccation: *Pucher M, B Palmia, D Baldan, M Mutz, L Coulson, M Bartoli, T Hein, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Biogeochemistry) Nutrient and DOM retention recovers within days after drying and rewetting in sediment perfusion cores*

Work package 4: Fluvial hydrodynamic and environmental modelling

For each study reach, simulations were carried out for three to four flow rates, from very low to medium flow (**Fig. 6**). The wetted area of the reaches at different flow rates was used to study the effect of changing flow regimes on biogeochemical processes (respiration, nutrient uptake potential). Respiration in the river bed had been measured as CO₂ production at multiple locations for dry sediments (<5% water content, representing sections exposed to the sun), moist but unsaturated sediments (10 - 15% water content, representing shaded sections) and flooded sediment. At Reitschulbach, water was remaining in pools when flow through the studied reach stopped. Thus, additional CO₂ production data was available for these areas. Three different scenarios were simulated: (1) shaded stream bed at different discharges (CO₂ production of non-flooded areas is equal to CO₂ production of moist sediments); (2) sun-exposed stream bed at different discharges (CO₂ production of non-flooded areas is equal to CO₂ production of sun-exposed sediments); (3) completely dry river

bed. The models showed reduced CO₂ production for lower discharges (**Fig. 7**), whereby the effect increased when assuming a reduction of the shading provided by the vegetation cover of the streambed. The nutrient uptake potential was estimated for (1) bankful (maximum uptake rates), (2) maximum contraction (with maximum uptake rates) whereby a small surface flow retained, and (3) maximum contraction after rewetting (reduced uptake rates) for the entire reaches (**Fig. 8**). In addition, we estimated the maximum release potential immediately after rewetting for bankful. Contraction had the highest reduction of reach-scale uptake in the Sucha, which also showed the highest reductions in the wetted area due to the larger width. Rewetting lead to changes in the ammonium uptake to release in all streams, while phosphorus was hardly affected (only Sucha shows a reduction). The potential release rates immediately after rewetting were higher than the maximum uptake rates except in the Sucha. However, as this release pulse is usually very short, no implications for the water quality are expected.

Figure 6 Water depth at Sucha at flow rates 3 l/s⁻¹, 31 l/s⁻¹, 60 l/s⁻¹, 127 l/s⁻¹ and 191 l/s⁻¹ (from left to right)

Figure 7 CO₂ production at different scenarios based on the hydrodynamic model: -o-: CO₂ production at different flow rates, shaded river bed; -x-: CO₂ production at different flow rates, river bed exposed to the sun; +: CO₂ production in the completely dry river bed.

Figure 8 Reach-scale nutrient uptake potential based on the hydrodynamic models for (1) bankful (maximum uptake rates), (2) maximum contraction (with maximum uptake rates), (3) rewetting (changed uptake rates) at bankful, and (4) release rates after rewetting at bankful. GB=Glaunigbach, RB=Reitschulbach, SU=Sucha.

Milestones:

- ✓ MS12: Complete set of results for all hydrodynamic numerical models
- ✓ MS13: Calculated self-purification capacity of reaches for wet/dry years
- ✓ MS14: Relationship discharge – self-purification capacity

WP5: Development of a guideline for water management authorities (in German)

Based on our results, we identified risk factors for a potential water quality deterioration during droughts which we incorporated in a guideline. In the guideline, we also suggest risk indicators to include into monitoring schemes of intermittent stream reaches and measures to protect drought effects on headwater streams. The guideline will be sent to the governments of Burgenland, Carinthia, Styria, and Lower Austria when it is released by the Klima und Energiefonds.

Milestone:

- ✓ MS15: Guideline; Weigelhofer, Tritthart (2021) „Vorschläge für intermittierende Fließgewässer zur Risikoabschätzung einer Verschlechterung der Wasserqualität infolge von Trockenperioden – Erkenntnisse aus dem Projekt PURIFY“

5. *Description of difficulties and solutions*

- Hyporheic water could not be sampled due to strong sediment clogging in our streams -> instead, we used analyses and experiments with hyporheic sediments to identify effects of drying on the hyporheic zone
- In-field nutrient addition experiments were only performed before the non-flow period in May but not after the non-flow period in October/November due to the seasonal changes over this long time period and thus lack of comparability -> instead, we performed laboratory uptake experiments

6. *Description of project highlights*

Scientific highlights:

The combination of field studies and laboratory experiments with benthic and hyporheic sediments and artificial drying and rewetting provides a **comprehensive picture of intermittent flow impacts** on microbial communities in temperate-climate streams that has not existed so far. Our paper by Feldbacher et al (submitted) does not only discuss the different effects of stagnant flow versus unsaturated conditions during intermittent flow but also incorporates these ideas into a **concept of intermittent flow impacts on sediment structures and processes along a gradient of moisture conditions**. Thus, the paper highlights new research directions on intermittent flow in temperate regions. Our hyporheic experiments (Pucher et al submitted) **provided new insights into resistance and recovery patterns of hyporheic processes** exposed to unsaturated conditions. Additionally, we show that benthic and hyporheic biofilms of temperate-climate streams are relatively resistant to desiccation stress and usually recover fast after rewetting **independent of flow history**, making them an ideal study object for research on changes of resource supply during non-saturated conditions (Coulson et al in prep; Pucher et al submitted).

International recognition:

The project results were presented at 11 **international conferences in total**.

Our project presentations in the internet and via personal communication attracted the interest of **colleagues to join the project** on their own funding. PhD student Beatrice Palmia (supervisor Marco Bartoli, University of Parma, Italy) joined the sediment column studies in 2019, with an own project focusing on the effects of drying and re-wetting on the N cycling in the hyporheic sediments. The results of her study are part of her PhD thesis. Miren Atristain (Supervisor Daniel von Schiller, University of Barcelona) conducted the flume experiments at WasserCluster in 2019. Her results will be published in a separate paper (currently in progress).

Katrin Attermeyer, working group leader at WasserCluster, **joined the field sampling** in 2019 and performed respiration experiments with the sediments on her own funding. A joint publication has been submitted to Freshwater Biology (see list of publications below).

Due to these collaborations, the **number of submitted manuscripts will be higher** than originally planned. The additional manuscripts are Attermeyer et al (submitted) and von Schiller et al (in prep).

Finally, we received **high international recognition** of our project within the Cost Action SMIRES and we were invited to the project DryFlux 2 about the CO₂ production of dry river beds with and without vegetation.

Educational impacts:

In total, 4 school students, 4 Bachelor students, 3 Master students, and 4 PhD students joined the project and finished their theses within the project. Thus, the project had a **high educational impact** on under-graduates despite the COVID-19 situation.

7. *Description and motivation of deviations from the original project application*

No deviations from the original application

Conclusions to be drawn from project results

- Overall, we conclude from our studies that temperate-climate streams can hold a relatively **high remaining moisture content** in the sediments which helps to keep the heterotrophic epipsammic biofilms intact and active. However, changes in the transport of solutes and gases during unsaturated conditions in the sediments affect biogeochemical processes. Thus, biogeochemical processes related to the self-purification capacity of the streams are significantly reduced immediately upon rewetting. However, the recovery of heterotrophic processes is usually fast and **no long-term effects** of intermittent flow have been observed on the activity of epipsammic benthic and hyporheic biofilms so far.
- The high moisture content is partly due to the temperate climate with dew during nights rewetting sediments even if no rainfall occurs. Further, sediment composition influences the moisture content with finer sediments being “wetter” than coarser sediments. Finally, moisture contents were higher in shaded reaches than in completely sun-exposed reaches. Thus, **shading is an effective management measure** to reduce drought effects on microbial communities and processes in benthic and hyporheic streams sediments.
- In contrast to heterotrophic epipsammic biofilms, autotrophic epilithic biofilms were strongly affected by intermittent flow. Algae showed decreased photosynthetic efficiencies and activities as well as reduced nutrient uptake capacities during and after the dry period, which did not recover within the two weeks of observation. The effects of desiccation were stronger in well-developed biofilms of open stream sections than in those of shaded sections where light generally restricted the growth of algae. Indeed, we found indications that restricted light availability superimposed desiccation effects. We conclude that **open sun-exposed stream reaches are more vulnerable** to intermittent flow than shaded reaches and thus **need special attention** of the management.
- Critical nutrient and DOC concentrations (and, thus, oxygen concentrations) may also arise in stream reaches where low discharge and increased water temperatures can lead to increased **release processes from the sediments**. Here, we observed increased concentrations in the water column especially in nutrient polluted small perennial streams during low discharge in summer. Thus, **more attention should be paid to low discharge and heating effects** on the release of substances from the sediments (including nutrients, organic matter, emerging pollutants, etc.) in small streams during summer droughts, independent of whether these streams are intermittent or perennial.
- In contrast to other studies, we have not observed any significant differences between intermittent and perennial reaches in the resistance and resilience of structural and functional microbial parameters to drying and rewetting. Currently, biofilms of intermittent

reaches do **not show any adaptation** to intermittent flow independent of the regularity of flow intermittency.

- From these results, we conclude that stream managers may treat stream reaches similarly independent of the respective frequency and duration of intermittent flow or the history of flow intermittency. Both intermittent and perennial streams exposed to high risks of low discharge and water heating should be monitored and protected, respectively. However, managers need to distinguish between streams with different geology and thus sediment composition as well as between streams with different pollution levels regarding both monitoring and management.

On the basis of the results obtained, the following further research steps can be suggested and will be taken by the project team:

- a. To study individual biogeochemical processes more closely regarding their response to drying and rewetting and their resistance, resilience and recovery in temperate-climate streams.
- b. To focus on low flow and warming impacts on the nutrient release potential of sediments and its significance for the water quality (internal eutrophication)
- c. To include interactions between drought impacts on the aquatic and terrestrial ecosystem, the social society and the economy

Currently, we are preparing two project proposals regarding the points a-b, while point c will be incorporated in an FWF-doc.fund proposal for a doctoral school.

Among the target groups that can draw relevant and interesting conclusions from the project results are water management authorities dealing with the protection and sustainable use of lotic ecosystems in dry regions and balanced water cycles. Further target groups are private environmental organisations or local governments that care for the protection of intermittent streams for environmental protection reasons, tourism, etc. Finally, the educational sector should be interested regarding climate change education.

Work and time schedule

The main field work took place in the years 2018 and 2019 as planned (see time schedule on the next page). During this time, geodetic and discharge data of three selected streams were collected for the hydro-dynamic models. The laboratory experiments and main parts of the hydro-dynamic modelling took place in summer 2019, also as originally planned. However, the start of the COVID-Pandemia in spring 2020 and the following strict restrictions in the year 2020 and less strict restrictions in 2021 led to delays especially in the data analyses, the data presentations and the publications (see deviations below). Nevertheless, most milestones could be fully delivered, only MS9 is still in preparation and has not been submitted yet.

Deviations from the original time schedule:

Due to the delayed start in April 2018, the time schedule was adapted. Work continued during the first two project years as planned despite the start of the **Covid-Pandemia** in spring 2020. However, work during the third project year was strongly restricted by the Pandemia and neither in-person meetings nor exchange with colleagues at conferences were possible in summer and autumn 2020. Thus, we requested an **extension of the project duration until 30/09/2021** which was authorized by the funding agency. Consequently, the time schedule was adapted to also allow for more time for in-depth data analyses and publications. Unfortunately, we experienced large delays in the review and acceptance of submitted manuscripts (e.g. Pucher et al.). Besides, the writing process took longer under COVID for some of our colleagues than usual leading also to delays in one manuscript (MS9). On the other hand, the project extension enabled us to submit one additional manuscript with contributions from Purify (Attermeyer et al) and another additional manuscript is being prepared (von Schiller et al).

In detail, the following milestones were either postponed due to the project extension or delayed due to COVID (see also time schedule on the next page):

- MS 5: The manuscript for the synthesis paper was postponed from 01/21 to autumn 2021 and was finally submitted in November by Feldbacher et al.
- MS 9: The manuscript was postponed from 07/20 to 08/21 but was further delayed due to Covid impacts. Currently, all data are statistically analysed and a draft with graphs exist. The manuscript should be submitted latest at the end of February.
- MS 11: The manuscript was postponed to summer 21 and submitted by Pucher et al. in August. It took until mid of November to find an editor for the reviewing process.
- MS 15: The guideline was postponed from 03/21 to September 2021. The MS is attached and needs approval of the Klima- und Energiefond before making it available for the public.

Annex

List of publications in the annex:

1. Weigelhofer G. & M. Tritthart (2019) Austrocknung von Bächen – eine Gefahr für die Wasserqualität? Österr Wasser- und Abfallw 2019 · 71:385–391.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00506-019-0580-2>
2. Guideline for managers
3. Title sheets of finished Bachelor- and Master-Theses
4. Report of the hydro-dynamic modelling

List of submitted publications incl. abstracts:

Pucher M, B Palmia, D Baldan, M Mutz, L Coulson, M Bartoli, T Hein, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Biogeochemistry on 23/08/2021) Nutrient and DOM retention recovers within days after drying and rewetting in sediment perfusion cores

Global change has led to reduced precipitation and increasing water abstraction, leading to perennial streams shifting to intermittency. Headwater streams in temperate regions are impacted by droughts that can lead to cessation of flow and desiccation. Droughts can malign microbial communities and constrain the self-purification in headwater streams.

Our aim was to reveal the effects of drying and rewetting on the retention and release of dissolved organic matter (DOM), dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), and soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP) in hyporheic sediments. We collected hyporheic sediments from 20 streams in Austria (10 perennial, 10 intermittent). The sediments were perfused in vertically arranged cores and connected to a flow-through water supply. We measured DOM, DIN and SRP in the outflow before and after a 7-week-drying phase and during low and elevated concentrations of these nutrients in the inflow. Our interests were the recovery of sediments from different streams and the differences in the response of intermittent and perennial streams to drying and re-wetting.

We observed a short, but high release peak and a reduced retention immediately after rewetting across all stream sediments. After two days, the release peak was almost gone. Likewise, the retention capacity had mostly recovered independent of the intermittency history of the stream. While the DOM released before drying was dominated by humic-like substances, rewetting caused a change towards protein-like fluorophores. The original DOM composition recovered until the end of the experiment. We consider the remaining sediment moisture key to the recovery of DOM and nutrient retention.

Feldbacher E, D von Schiller, M Mutz, L Coulson, M Tritthart, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Freshwater Biology on 11/11/2021) Impacts of intermittent flow on benthic biofilm processes and structures in temperate-climate streams

Due to climate change and excessive water use, drought periods have spread across Europe, shifting perennial streams to intermittent flow regimes even in temperate zones.

However, temperate-climate streams may be affected differently by intermittent flow than streams in more arid regions due to a higher remaining moisture content in the sediments. Our study aimed to expand the knowledge on short- and long-term effects of flow intermittence on biofilm structures and processes in temperate-climate streams. Specifically, we explored whether (1) benthic biofilm parameters differed between intermittent and perennial stream reaches before and during the period of interrupted surface flow, (2) epipsammic and epilithic biofilm communities responded differently to drying due to different exposure, and (3) biofilm structures and processes were equally affected by surface flow disruption.

We sampled epipsammic (fine sediments < 4 mm) and epilithic (stone surfaces) biofilms on the sediment surface of both perennial and intermittent stream reaches before (May/June) and during the non-flow period (August/September) in a temperate region in Austria. We analysed structures (moisture content, bacterial abundances, chlorophyll-a concentrations, pigment composition, extra-cellular enzyme activities) and processes (bacterial respiration, photosynthetic efficiency, net nutrient uptake and release potential) in the dry and wet sediments, respectively.

Even after > 2 months of disrupted surface flow, the average gravimetric moisture content was about 10% in the unsaturated sediments of the intermittent reaches. Intermittent reaches did not differ from perennial reaches in spring and were hardly affected by the non-flow phase in summer. Biofilm structures only showed significant differences between perennial and intermittent streams in the relative proportion of carotenoids. Among the analysed biogeochemical processes, epipsammic and epilithic biofilms showed significant reductions of the respiratory capacity (approx. -50%) and the photosynthetic efficiency, respectively. However, the photosynthetic efficiency was also reduced in perennial reaches in summer, indicating that shading effects may have overlaid desiccation stress on epilithic biofilms. Unsaturated sediments of intermittent reaches showed an increased ammonium release and a significantly reduced ammonium uptake upon re-wetting compared to the wet sediments of perennial reaches. However, this pattern was not observed for dissolved inorganic phosphorus.

We conclude that high remaining moisture content in the benthic sediments of temperate-climate streams helps to keep biofilm communities intact even during prolonged non-flow phases. However, changes in the transport of solutes and gases during stagnant and unsaturated conditions in the sediments affect biogeochemical processes.

In the face of increasing water scarcity in future, it is important to analyse the multiple effects of intermittent flow on streams that have started to fall dry only recently. Here, streams in temperate zones provide an ideal opportunity to study the effects of changed transport patterns and altered resource supply on stream biofilms during different stages of disrupted surface flow under high remaining moisture conditions.

Attermeyer K, A Harjung, J Schelker, G Weigelhofer (submitted to *Freshwater Biology* on 19/11/2021) Phosphorus can, but does not necessarily stimulate terrestrial carbon degradation in stream hyporheic zones. – Only with contributions of PURIFY

List of manuscripts in preparation:

Coulson L, Feldbacher E, Weigelhofer G (in prep; submission latest at the end of February)
Similar response of biofilms to drying in perennial and intermittent reaches of temperate-climate streams (Working title)

Von Schiller D, et al. (in prep) Effects of intermittent flow on epilithic biofilms of intermittent and perennial temperate-climate streams – a laboratory flumes study (Working title)

2 Presentation of Costs

Table of costs for the entire project duration

The following table provides an aggregated overview of the costs incurred by the applicant and the project partners throughout the entire project duration, broken down by staff costs, capital expenditure, travel expenses, administrative and material expenses, and third-party costs. It must correspond to the cost accounting form (annexed to the support contract and/or available for downloading under www.publicconsulting.at).

All figures in EURO.

Cost category	Eligible total costs according to contract	Cumulative costs during the project term Total costs for the consortium*	Applicant Costs incurred during the project term from 01/04/2018 to 30/09/2021	Partner 1 Costs incurred during the project term from 01/04/2018 to 30/09/2021	Partner 2 Costs incurred during the project term from 01/04/2018 to 30/09/2021
Staff costs	170800**	186303.26	121915.32	64387.94	0
Capital expenditure	0	0	0	0	0
Travel expenses	13021	10328.21	7520.76	191.30	2616.15
Administrative and material expenses	65711**	48113.49	45049.53	0	3063.96
Third-party costs	0	2861.54	0	0	2861.54
Total	249532	247606.5	174485.61	64579.24	8541.65

* Sum total of costs incurred / cost category of the applicant and all partners

** WCL requested a reclassification of 15.000,- from material expenses to staff costs which was granted by the Klima und Energiefond.

Statement of costs for the entire project duration

WasserCluster Lunz: The majority of the personal costs was used for the PhD students involved in the field sampling, the laboratory experiments, the sample analyses, data analyses, and manuscript writing. The rest of the personal costs were used for TAs for general (e.g. nutrient and DOC data) and specific lab analyses (e.g. bacterial abundances, HPLC). Regarding the people originally planned in the project, Elisabeth Bondar-Kunze went

on maternity leave and a PhD substituted her. The reclassification of material costs to personal costs were used for further sample analyses and in-depth statistical analyses. Travel expenses were slightly higher than originally planned for the applicant because field trips included accommodation in the study region to reduce emissions by driving. Travel expenses covered the trips to the locations, accommodation at the sampling sites, and accommodation at WCL for the analyses as well as conference fees (and to a small amount travel and accommodation during conferences before the Covid pandemia). Material costs included costs for equipment for the field sampling, for the lab experiments, and analytical costs.

Partner 1 used the personal costs for the development of the hydrodynamic models. Partner 1 used lower travel costs than planned due to the postponement of conferences to 2022.

The travel budget of **partner 2** planned originally for Daniel Von Schiller was used to cover the travel expenses of Miren Atristain during her stay in Lunz for the experiments. The material expenses covered the analytical costs at the University of Barcelona. The DNA analyses which were originally included in the material costs had to be reclassified as third-party costs due to the change of partner 2 (see below).

Cost reclassification

WCL requested a reclassification of 15 000.- material costs to personal costs (accepted by the funding source).

Due to the new position of Daniel von Schiller at the University of Barcelona, we requested a change of partner 2 from the University of the Basque Country to the University of Barcelona. The change was accepted by Klimafond, all partner contracts were adapted, and the budget was transferred accordingly.

Due to the change of partner 2 from the University of the Basque Country to the University of Barcelona, the DNA-analyses done at the University of the Basque Country had to be reclassified as third-party costs (instead of material costs).

3 Utilization

– **Publications:**

Conference presentations:

1. Weigelhofer G, D von Schiller, M Mutz, M Tritthart (2018) Effects of desiccation on the self-purification capacity of headwater streams. 1st Meeting of the Iberian Ecological Society (SIBECOL) from 4-7 February in Barcelona.
2. Weigelhofer, G.; Von Schiller, D.; Mutz, M.; Tritthart, M. (2019): Effects of drought on the self-purification capacity of temperate headwater streams. 11th Symposium for European Freshwater Sciences (SEFS), Zagreb, Croatia, Jun 30 – Jul 5
3. Weigelhofer, G; Ziegler, L; Waberer, M; von Schiller, D; Mutz, M; Tritthart, M; (2019): Effects of drying and re-wetting on biofilm processes in temperate headwater streams. 6th Biennial Symposium of the International Society of River Sciences, SEPT 8-12, 2019, Vienna, AUSTRIA
4. Waberer, M.; Ziegler, L.; Senitzka, M.; Hein, T.; Weigelhofer, G.; (2019): Effects of desiccation on benthic and hyporheic microbial activities in temperate streams. [poster] 6th Biennial Symposium of ISRS, Vienna, Austria, Sep 8 – 13
5. Pucher, M.; Hein, T.; Weigelhofer, G. (2020): Nutrient and organic matter retention in the hyporheic zone during drying and re-wetting in a mesocosm experiment. European Geoscience Union (EGU) General Assembly 2020, Vienna, Austria, online, May 4 – 8
6. Weigelhofer, G.; Pucher, M. (2020): Effects of intermittency and land use on the in-stream phosphorus and organic carbon uptake. European Geoscience Union (EGU) General Assembly 2020, Vienna, Austria, online, May 4 – 8
7. Von Schiller, D., Atristain, M., Elosegi, A. & Weigelhofer, G. (2020) Differential responses of biofilms from perennial and intermittent streams to drying. Murcia 26-29th October 2020, online.
8. Posterpresentation on the Klimatag 2020 (online)
9. Pucher, M; Palmia, B; Bartoli, M; Baldan, D; Weigelhofer, G; (2021): Effects of drying and rewetting on hyporheic organic matter and nutrient retention in sediment perfusion cores. ASLO Aquatic Sciences Meeting, 22-27 June, 2021, Online (Vienna)
10. Von Schiller, D; Atristain, M; Elosegi, A; Zazaonandia, A; Weigelhofer, G; (2021): Differential response of biofilms from perennial and intermittent streams to drying. 12th Symposium for European Freshwater Sciences, SFS, 25-30 July, 2021, Online (Dublin)
11. Weigelhofer, G; Pucher, M; (2021): Shading can buffer short- and long-term effects of drying on benthic processes. 12th Symposium for European Freshwater Sciences, SFS, 25-30 July, 2021, Online (Dublin)
12. Tritthart M., Wildt D., Weigelhofer G. (2021) A model-based framework for the estimation of the self-purifying capacity of intermittent streams under a changing climate. IAHR 2021 (postponed to 2022)

Bachelor-, Master- and PhD-Theses completed within PURIFY:

1. Kilian Glösl, Dominik Barbi, Serena Tabirca, Valentina Enengl (2020) Untersuchung von Biofilmen von trockenfallenden österreichischen Bächen. **SchoolDiploma Thesis**, HLUW Yspertal.
2. Charlotta von Bychelberg (2021) Die Auswirkungen saisonaler Austrocknung auf die Nährstoffkonzentration in Fließgewässern. Untersuchung der maximalen Aufnahmerate von Ammonium in Bachsedimenten im Rahmen des Projekts Purify. **Bac-Thesis**, Boku.
3. Pia Karbiener (2021) Einfluss der Austrocknung und Wiedervernässung auf die P, N und DOC Aufnahme- und Abgaberrate des Sediments intermittierender Flüsse. **Bac-Thesis**, Boku.
4. Sophie Ehrlinger (2021) Die maximale Phosphoraufnahmekapazität unter Austrocknung und Wiedervernässung von Sedimenten aus natürlich intermittierenden Bächen. **Bac-Thesis**, Boku.
5. Stefanie Nikl (2021) Die potenziellen Auswirkungen des Klimawandels auf die mikrobielle Respiration von intermittierenden Flüssen (Project RURIFY). **Bac-Thesis**, Boku
6. Magdalena Senitza (2019) Effects of desiccation on heterotrophic microorganisms in benthic sediments in intermittent streams, **MSc Thesis**, FH Technikum Wien
7. Jakob Lechner (2019) Effects of desiccation on the self-purification capacity of headwater streams, **MSc Thesis**, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien, November 2019
8. Lisa-Marie Ziegler (2020) Effects of desiccation on heterotrophic microbial activity in hyporheic sediments, **MSc Thesis**, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien
9. Beatrice Palmia (2020) Effects of hydrological intermittency on the functioning of lotic ecosystems. **PhD Thesis**, University of Parma, Italy (with contributions of PURIFY).
10. Matthias Pucher (2021) Organic carbon cycling in streams: process understanding and impacts through agriculture and droughts. **PhD Thesis**, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien. (with contributions of PURIFY)
11. Daniel Wildt (2022) Hydrodynamic and Sediment Transport Computational Fluid Dynamics Modelling on Different Scales. **PhD Thesis** (in finalization), Universität für Bodenkultur Wien. (with contributions of PURIFY)
12. Laura Coulson (in prep) Effects of desiccation on biofilms in temperate-climate streams (working title), Universität für Bodenkultur Wien. (with contributions of PURIFY)

Publications

1. Weigelhofer G. & M. Tritthart (2019) Austrocknung von Bächen – eine Gefahr für die Wasserqualität? Österr Wasser- und Abfallw 2019 · 71:385–391. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00506-019-0580-2>
2. Pucher M, B Palmia, D Baldan, M Mutz, L Coulson, M Bartoli, T Hein, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Biogeochemistry) Nutrient and DOM retention recovers within days after drying and rewetting in sediment perfusion cores

3. Feldbacher E, D von Schiller, M Mutz, L Coulson, M Tritthart, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Freshwater Biology) Impacts of intermittent flow on benthic biofilm processes and structures in temperate-climate streams
4. Attermeyer K, A Harjung, J Schelker, G Weigelhofer (submitted to Freshwater Biology) Phosphorus can, but does not necessarily stimulate terrestrial carbon degradation in stream hyporheic zones.
5. Coulson L, Feldbacher E, Weigelhofer G (in prep) Similar response of biofilms to drying in perennial and intermittent reaches of temperate-climate streams (Working title)
6. Von Schiller D, et al. (in prep) Effects of intermittent flow on epilithic biofilms of intermittent and perennial temperate-climate streams – a laboratory flumes study (Working title)

Medienberichte und Radio-Interviews:

- Die Presse - Was geht alles den Bach hinunter... (02.05.2020)
- Ö1 - Dimensionen - Wie klimafit sind unsere Bäche? (14.10.2021)
- Ö1 - Radiokolleg - Die Quellen sauberen Wassers (11.10.2021); with contributions
- derstandard.at - Dünger und Dürre setzen Grundwasser zu (20.07.2019); with contributions
- **Tips** - [Projekte am WasserCluster Lunz](#) (09.08.2018); with contributions
- Ö1 - Radiokolleg - Trinkwasser in Österreich (1.2. - 4.2.2021); with contributions

– **Market:** no economic potential

– **Doctoral dissertations:**

The following doctoral students were partly involved in the PURIFY project:

Beatrice Palmia (2020) Effects of hydrological intermittency on the functioning of lotic ecosystems. PhD Thesis, University of Parma, Italy.

Matthias Pucher (2021) Organic carbon cycling in streams: process understanding and impacts through agriculture and droughts. PhD Thesis, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien

Daniel Wildt (2022) Hydrodynamic and Sediment Transport Computational Fluid Dynamics Modelling on Different Scales. PhD Thesis (in finalization), Universität für Bodenkultur Wien.

Laura Coulson (in prep) Effects of desiccation on biofilms in temperate-climate streams (working title), Universität für Bodenkultur Wien.

4 Outlook

Low flow and warming can affect the potential of stream sediments to act as sinks or sources for nutrients and dissolved organic matter, depending also on the respective geology and land use. While diffuse inputs from agriculture and point sources determine the water quality during medium and high flow, internal eutrophication through release from the sediments may become the key factor for water quality during low flow. Research is needed on the interactive effects of local factors and climatic conditions on the sink – source function of stream sediments to better predict water quality deterioration as consequence of droughts and warming in the future.

Future research also needs to focus on the resilience and resistance of lotic ecosystems to more frequent prolonged droughts and catastrophic floods across spatial scales. Here, impact cascades and feed-backs along food chains and/or from catchment to choriotope scale would provide information about the overall resilience of the system, the vulnerability of individual nodes or connections, and the potential changes of key players due to climate change.

For the management, further research is needed on strategies to protect and manage lotic systems vulnerable to drought impacts. Risk indicators at different scales, vulnerability assessments for different system components, monitoring schemes that cross the terrestrial-aquatic interface (catchment to reach), and a toolbox of sustainable measures and their effects would support managers in identifying “weak” units and linkages in the system and selecting the most appropriate measures.

5 Signature

I herewith confirm that the report in its entirety has been accepted by the project partners.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, reading 'Gabriele Weiglhofer', is written over a horizontal line.

__Lunz am See, 13.12.2021__

Place, date

Signature of the applicant (coordinator)

Please note: the signature has to be scanned in and inserted into the document.